

Ocean Frontier Institute Visiting Fellowship report

by Tim Kiessling (Fall 2024)

During the months of August to November 2024 I had the chance to visit and work with the research group of [Professor Tony R. Walker](#) at the [School for Resource and Environmental Studies](#) (SRES) at [Dalhousie University](#) in Halifax, Canada. At the beginning of the year I applied to the [Visiting Fellowship program of the Ocean Frontier Institute](#), who are a partner of [Kiel University](#) (my home university), and was awarded the fellowship. I was thrilled to go to Canada, a place I intended to visit, since my dad called it “big Scandinavia” when I was young.

During my four months at Dal, I had the chance to get to know the highly interdisciplinary work of the people from SRES, often working on challenging environmental and societal issues and to present my work on plastic pollution, science communication, and collaborative research approaches (such as citizen science and community science) to students from different fields (see the list of activities and events in Appendix 1).

One of my highlights was the implementation of the [Plastic Pirates program](#) and the subsequent collaboration with schoolkids to investigate the plastic pollution of lakes and the ocean in Nova Scotia: through the program [Let’s Talk Science](#) I was able to get in contact with teachers from seven schools and overall more than 200 school students. These fourth to sixth grader’s were a lively bunch and excited “TO DO SCIENCE”, which was their frequent response, when I asked them for the objective of our excursion to the lakes and ocean. I was surprised by their motivation to get out on cold and, at times, rainy days to collect and sort through plenty of plastic litter. The results of this program can be seen in the report “[Plastic Pirates in Nova Scotia – Litter pollution results for fall 2024](#)”.

I also had the opportunity to give a Directed Study course revolving around the topic of returnable food packaging to reduce the use of single-use plastic packaging (the resulting manuscript was submitted to the journal [Cambridge Prisms: Plastics](#)), was involved in the thesis defence of two students of the Master of Environmental Studies, and [gave a public talk](#) organized by the [Department of Information Science](#) (an article related to this talk was published on the blog of the [Environmental Information: Use and Influence](#) group).

There were plenty of chances for networking, too, for example during chats in the Graduate Student suite of SRES, at a Professional Development Day for school teachers hosted by the [International Ocean Institute](#), during the [Sustainable Ocean Conference 2024](#), at the [50th anniversary celebration of](#)

[SRES](#), during talks with members of the [Canadian Ocean Literacy Coalition \(COLC\)](#), the [Ocean School](#), and participants of two visual science communication workshops.

In summary, at Dal I had the opportunity to reflect the relevance of my work in a new country and different academic setting, to establish new work contacts, and to collaborate with researchers in interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary contexts.

Apart from work, I was also able to enjoy many other things Halifax had to offer (for example taking part in lively Capoeira classes and discovering cafés, try [tart & soul!](#)), explored some of the beautiful nature of Nova Scotia, and – most importantly – found new friends. The four months at Dal and in Halifax were an engaging and colourful time and I am deeply grateful to have been in touch with so many beautiful and inspiring people!

Acknowledgments

A lot of people contributed to making my research stay at Dal and my life in Halifax such a memorable and rich experience, thank you! Tony, your enthusiastic approach to research is refreshing and a big motivation, thanks for involving me wherever possible, for networking opportunities and making a habit of working outside the academic setting. Maya, you did an amazing job coordinating the school visits and establishing contacts to teachers, without you I couldn't have done it! All the teachers and schoolchildren and volunteers, listed in the [report of the Let's Talk Science Plastic Pirates collaboration](#), were very engaged and it was a pleasure collaborating with them! Brenda, Denette, Khoi, Paula, and Tracey, thank you for facilitating everything around my stay, that is much appreciated! Bertrum, thank you for enriching chats, creating a very welcoming atmosphere for visiting researchers, and the opportunity to give a public lecture! Similarly, thank you, Boris, Georgia, Heather, Jane, Laurel, Kate, Kate, Melanie, Michelle, Mike, Nathan, Peter, Sandra, and Rachael, as well as other SRES researchers, for engaging conversations and including me wherever possible. Some of you have also entrusted your students to me for lectures and sharing my research – it was a great experience seeing their curiosity, enthusiasm and engagement! Arden, it was a pleasure to collaborate with you and advance on a research project together! Alex, Ben, Justine, and Keahna, thanks for chats and talks about everything, including research and connecting me to other people at Dal – you are all very involved researchers and I am impressed by your dedication and the relevance of your work. Finally, my colleagues at Kiel University supported my research stay at Dal, thank you, Frauke, Janto, Katrin, and Sinja! Ilka and Martin, I am very grateful that you have supported my application for the

fellowship and facilitated my research work over the past years. Many wonderful people made my stay so memorable outside of university, I am very happy we crossed paths! Thank you Alizee, Bishoy, Daniel, Dawn, Débora, Heather, Kat, Khoi, Julia, Maria, Martina, Michael, Otavio, Ross, and Simon. I am also very grateful to my family and friends in Germany, they made coming back from Halifax less difficult.

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Kiel, 31st of March 2025

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Appendix 1: List of activities, events, lectures and publications related to the Visiting Fellowship

- Tim Kiessling, Arden Goodfellow, Tony R. Walker (1st of September to 4th of December 2024). Directed Study course at the School for Resource and Environmental Studies, titled “Why not deposit-return all plastic food packaging?”. One student participated.
- Tim Kiessling, Tracey Woodhouse (9th of September 2024) Event “Doodle your Research - An exercise in visual science communication” (Ocean Frontier Institute, Dalhousie University, Halifax, Canada). 6 participants.
- Tim Kiessling (25th of September 2024). Guest lecture for the Resource and Environmental Management course of Michelle Adams. “Research challenge: publishing data by schoolchildren” (Dalhousie University, Halifax, Canada). 13 attendants, lecture available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13835058>.
- Tim Kiessling (7th of October 2024) Presentation "Reflecting on communication with teachers empowering their students in collaborative research projects" held for the TransCoastal Adaptations Centre for Nature-Based Solutions (online). 14 attendants, lecture available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13871915>.
- Tim Kiessling (8th of October 2024) Presentation “Reflecting your own role as researchers in community science studies” for the Research Design and Methods class held by Kate Sherren (Dalhousie University, Halifax, Canada). 9 attendants, lecture available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13921763>.
- Tim Kiessling (8th of October 2024) Presentation "Enabling schoolchildren to participate in research – experiences from a citizen science program in Germany" for the Community-based co-management class held by Rachael Cadman (Dalhousie University, Halifax, Canada). 10 attendants, lecture available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13921892>.
- Tim Kiessling, Maya Goldchtaub, Angela Gillis (10th of October 2024). Plastic Pirates sampling with Cunard Junior High School at Williams Lake (Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada). 24 schoolstudents plus 2 teachers participated.
- Tim Kiessling, Maya Goldchtaub, Erin Delaney (16th of October 2024). Plastic Pirates sampling with Beechville-Lakeside-Timberlea School at Half Mile Lake (Timberlea, Nova Scotia, Canada). 20 schoolstudents plus 1 teacher participated.
- Tim Kiessling (17th of October 2024) Presentation “Plastic pollution by textiles – citizen science as a solution?” Input for the Environmental Decision Making class of Laurel Schut and Nathan Ayer (Dalhousie University, Halifax, Canada). 32 attendants, lecture available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13942649>.
- Tim Kiessling (29th of October 2024) Presentation “Communication is key in community science programs involving schoolkids and teachers” Input for The Community as a Living Lab class of Heather Cray (Dalhousie University, Halifax, Canada). 7 attendants, lecture available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14003194>.
- Tim Kiessling, Maya Goldchtaub, Laura Washburn, Hailey Meade (30th of October 2024). Plastic Pirates sampling with Rockingstone Heights School at Kidston Lake (Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada). 42 schoolstudents plus 4 teachers/supervisors participated.
- Tim Kiessling, Maya Goldchtaub, Crystal Isert, Nicole Saulnier (5th of November 2024). Plastic Pirates sampling with Leslie Thomas Junior High School at First Lake (Lower Sackville, Nova Scotia, Canada). 29 schoolstudents plus 6 teachers/supervisors participated.
- Tim Kiessling, Maya Goldchtaub, Tara MacDonald, Bria Woods, Neil Daigle, Beverly Anthony, Jennifer Blackburn, Kathy Laprise, Angela Akpan, Sarah Thorpe, Emma-Joy Swan (6th of November 2024). Plastic Pirates sampling with Cavalier Drive School at First Lake (Lower Sackville, Nova Scotia, Canada). 38 schoolstudents plus 9 teachers/supervisors participated.
- Tim Kiessling, Maya Goldchtaub, Fiyinfolu Onososen, Elizabeth Cousineau, Parisana Low (12th of November 2024) Plastic Pirates sampling at Chocolate Lake (Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada). 3 university students participated.
- Tim Kiessling, Maya Goldchtaub, Mary-Emma Murphy (14th of November 2024) Plastic Pirates sampling with Crichton Park School at Lake Banook (Dartmouth, Nova Scotia, Canada). 22 schoolstudents plus 7 teachers/supervisors participated.
- Tim Kiessling, Maya Goldchtaub, Jasmine Figg, Claire McKenzie (15th of November 2024) Plastic Pirates sampling with École Shannon Park School at Shannon Park (Dartmouth, Nova Scotia, Canada). 46 schoolstudents plus 8 teachers/supervisors participated.
- Tim Kiessling, Laurel Schut, Mike Lancaster (16th of November 2024) Plastic Pirates sampling with volunteers from the St. Margarets Bay Stewardship Association (St. Margarets Bay, Nova Scotia, Canada). 8 volunteers participated.

Tim Kiessling (19th of November 2024). Presentation “Can the Public Contribute to Plastic Pollution Policy-Making through Community Science? A vision for Participatory Legislation” Lecture organized by the Department of Information Science at Dalhousie University (Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada), 36 attendants, lecture available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14238270>.

Tim Kiessling, Haley Geizer (29th of November 2024) Visual science communication workshop – research and outreach graphics using Inkscape (Dalhousie University, Halifax, Canada). 5 participants.

List of publications

The fellowship allowed me to pursue work on the following publications

Tim Kiessling, Maya Goldchtaub, Tony R. Walker (23rd of January 2025) Plastic Pirates in Nova Scotia – Litter pollution results for fall 2024, report available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14507148>.

Tim Kiessling (12th of February 2025) Can Schoolchildren Contribute to Research and Policy-making Through Citizen Science? Environmental Information: Use and Influence blog, <https://eiui.ca/can-schoolchildren-contribute-to-research-and-policy-making-through-citizen-science/>.

Tim Kiessling, Christina Claussen, Katrin Kruse, Carolin Enzingmüller, Kerstin Kremer, Katrin Knickmeier, Sinja Dittmann, Hinrich Schulenburg, Ilka Parchmann (accepted to be published in the Journal of Science Communication) How can we enable school students to learn and participate in science engagement initiatives? Roles and tasks of enablers.

Janto Schönberg, Marianne Böhm-Beck, Štefan Trdan, Mateja Grego, Doris Knoblauch, Mandy Hinzmann, Sinja Dittmann, Katrin Knickmeier, Uroš Robič, Martin Thiel, Tim Kiessling (submitted to Aquatic Conservation) Public participation in EU legislation? Recommendations for involving citizen scientists in anthropogenic litter research within the Water Framework Directive.

Arden Goodfellow, Tony R. Walker, Tim Kiessling (submitted to Cambridge Prisms: Plastic) Why Don't we Reuse our Food Packaging? Insights from Two Organizations Implementing Packaging Return Systems to Avoid Single-Use Plastics.